

Utilization of Film Viewing as a Scaffolding Strategy to Enhance the Comprehension Skills Among Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences Students

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ABSTRACT: The majority of information is delivered through text; therefore, being able to read and comprehend is crucial for learners to survive and comprehend how society functions. Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill required for academic performance and lifelong learning. Since reading comprehension is essential to academic success. Teachers always look for new and creative ways to help their students improve in this area. In this study, the researcher employed the Film viewing as a scaffolding strategy to improve reading comprehension such as literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation and appreciation skills among 30 Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences Based on the results of the study, the findings revealed that there is a significant difference in reorganization and evaluation skills between the pre-test and post-test activities thus these variables are partially sustained. Likewise, there was no significant difference in literal, inferential and appreciation skills which signifies that the use of film viewing as a scaffolding strategy improved these skills. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

KEYWORDS : film viewing, scaffolding strategy, comprehension skills

INTRODUCTION

Reading is essential at all educational system levels. This is because reading is a requirement for every course, and improving academic performance is the result. People may read for various reasons, including information, knowledge, leisure, pleasure, and relaxation. Current studies demonstrate how our understanding of reading as a complex cognitive process is developing. Stress that reading comprehension requires critical thinking, reasoning, and inferential skills. This suggests that reading develops broader critical thinking abilities in addition to improving comprehension.

Comprehension is the cornerstone of learning across all subjects. Without strong comprehension skills, students struggle to grasp new concepts, retain information, and apply knowledge effectively. Investigating these skills helps educators identify gaps and implement strategies to strengthen students' ability to understand and process information.

Similarly, students with strong comprehension skills generally perform better academically. They can interpret questions accurately, understand reading materials, and articulate their thoughts clearly. By investigating these skills, educators can develop targeted interventions to support students who are struggling, thereby improving overall academic outcomes.

Since reading comprehension is essential to academic success, teachers always look for new and creative ways to help their students improve in this area. Using film viewing as a scaffolding approach is one such method that has gained popularity recently. A dynamic and engaging approach to reading comprehension is provided by multimedia resources, which include pictures, films, animations, and interactive digital tools. These materials give students more context and various ways to understand complex ideas. Teachers may efficiently scaffold students' comprehension skill development by giving multimedia resources that are thoughtfully created to match students' present abilities while presenting chances for advancement within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD).

Teachers can design interactive and captivating learning experiences that accommodate various learners' cognitive processes and learning styles by utilizing film resources consistent with these beliefs. Information retention and comprehension are improved when verbal and visual components are combined because they activate the visual and verbal processing processes. Moreover, a better understanding is promoted by the meaningful links between newly learned material and pre-existing mental frameworks thanks to the activation of prior knowledge facilitated by schema theory.

The primary reason for conducting the study is likely to investigate and assess the effectiveness of using film viewing as a scaffolding strategy to improve reading comprehension skills of students. Scaffolding strategies involve providing support or guidance to learners as they develop new skills or knowledge, and film viewing might be considered a different approach to enhance

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comprehension among learners. The study aims to contribute to whether incorporating film elements can positively impact the comprehension abilities of students, particularly Grade 11-HUMSS students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to find out the effect of Film Viewing as a Scaffolding Strategy to improve the comprehension skills of Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students in the School Year 2023-2024. The study focused on one section in Grade 11 HUMSS. This study tested the significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of the respondents in literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation and appreciation before and after using film viewing as a scaffolding strategy.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a pre- experimental research design specifically the pre-test post-test design to determine whether the student-respondents' comprehension skills have improved after using the Film Viewing as a Scaffolding Strategy.

Pre-experimental research resembles experimental research but is not accurate experimental research. Although the independent variable is manipulated, participants are not randomly assigned to conditions or orders of conditions. The pre-experimental research does not compare groups and there is no control group

The pre-test was given to students to assess their comprehension skills before utilizing the film viewing as a scaffolding strategy. Post-test was given after the use of film viewing as a scaffolding strategy to determine if comprehension skills have improved during the conduct of the study.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To determine the effect of the film viewing as a scaffolding strategy to improve the comprehension skills among students, pre-test was prepared focusing on the five comprehension skills such as literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation and appreciation.

Four (4) Lesson Exemplars which were used to implement the strategies were crafted. These cater the four (4) learning competencies of grade 11 HUMSS students of fourth quarter for the school year 2023-2024.

Each set of Lesson Exemplars indicate five learning competencies that were targeted to be achieved. The use of film viewing for every lesson were specifically placed in the development part of the lesson wherein the researcher intended to capture students' interest before the discussion of the lesson. After each lesson, students were given printed reading materials with the same skills for them to answer independently.

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

The researcher conducted the study during the fourth quarter of the school year 2023-2024. The lessons were based on the MELCS provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) and teacher's IDEA Lesson Exemplar (LE). The lessons were discussed using different strategies during activities to make the students engaged individually or in groups. Film viewing strategy were used during the period of experiment and strategy was divided into lessons/topics for the whole quarter.

The researcher made used of an adapted modified test to measure students' comprehension skills. The instrument was validated first by the subject specialist. For the content and face validity, three external validators checked the said instrument. The researcher incorporated the suggestions provided by the validators. Afterwards, the researcher, with the approval of her adviser and the statistician, then conducted the pilot testing to ensure test reliability. There were twelve (12) Grade 11 students who participated in the conduct of pilot testing. The responses were tallied and subjected for item analysis. The researcher used the result of item analysis to revise or even alter some of the test questions. After the instrument was finalized, the researcher administered the pretest to the respondents as the first assessment of their comprehension skills.

During the experiment, the researcher administered the pre-test to the target group of Grade 11 HUMSS students. Then, the researcher had the intervention implementation started with lesson plan development. The researcher created a detailed lesson plan for four-week period, integrating film viewing as a scaffolding strategy. In addition, the researcher outlined specific film clips to be used, discussion questions, and activities to reinforce comprehension skills. Then, the researcher implemented the film viewing and discussion. The researcher facilitated guided discussion to help students connect the visual and textual elements. The students were encouraged to analyze the film's plot, characters, themes, and messages.

The students had the reading and comprehension activities after the film viewing. The researcher assigned reading materials aligned with the film's themes. Then, activities that promote active reading and critical skills were conducted such as literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation and appreciation.

Posttest was given to the respondents who have undergone the experiment after the period of lessons stated in the lesson exemplar.

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After the pretest and posttest, the researcher then collected the data, and submitted to the statistician for the treatment. It was then tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

For ethical considerations, the researcher sought the permission from the Division Office Superintendent, District Supervisor and the head of the school to conduct the study and submit letter of consent to utilize the chosen students who will serve as the respondents.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

After the gathering of the data, these were subjected for statistical treatment. The researcher tabulated the raw data. Then it was submitted to statistics center for the statistical tools to be used for better analysis and discussions. The researcher then, analyzed and interpreted the results.

Aside from the mean scores, to get the significant difference of the pretest of respondents, Test of difference was used. T-test for dependent and independent means for inferential analyses were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pretest Scores of the respondents before using film as a scaffolding strategy

Table 1

Mean pretest scores of the respondents before using the film as a scaffolding strategy in reading comprehension

Measure	Very Proficient (5)	Proficient (4)	Moderately Proficient (3)	Less Proficient (2)	Not Proficient (1)	Total (N)	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Literal	7 (23%)	11 (37%)	6 (20%)	2 (7%)	4 (13%)	30	3.5	Moderately proficient
Reorganization	1 (3%)	10 (33%)	12 (40%)	7 (23%)	0 (0%)	30	3.17	Moderately proficient
Inferential	0 (0%)	6 (20%)	11 (37%)	10 (33%)	3 (10%)	30	2.67	Moderately proficient
Evaluation	0 (0%)	5 (17%)	11 (37%)	7 (23%)	7 (23%)	30	2.47	Less proficient
Appreciation	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (37%)	11 (37%)	8 (26%)	30	2.10	Not proficient

Legend:

VP-Very Proficient (5) ; P-Proficient (4) ; MP-Moderately Proficient (3) ; LP-Less Proficient (2) ; NP-Not Proficient (1)

Table 1 includes the calculated mean scores for each area of reading comprehension where each skill is associated with a mean score and verbal interpretation that reflects the level of proficiency. Literal and reorganization skills are relatively strong, while inferential, evaluation, and appreciation skills indicate a need for improvement where most measures fall within the "Moderately proficient" range, with appreciation being the lowest at "Not proficient."

Literal Comprehension has a Mean Score of 3.50 interpreted as Moderately Proficient. This means that the respondents demonstrated moderate proficiency in literal comprehension.

Moreover, in terms of Reorganization, it has a Mean Score of 3.17 which is interpreted as Moderately Proficient. The moderate proficiency in reorganization indicates that respondents can summarize and restructure information but may struggle with more complex tasks.

In addition, Inferential Comprehension has a Mean Score: 2.67 interpreted as Less Proficient. The lower mean score in inferential comprehension suggests significant room for improvement. This emphasizes the need for targeted interventions, such as guided discussions and explicit teaching of inferential strategies, to support students in making connections beyond the text.

However, Evaluation has a Mean Score of 2.47 interpreted as Less Proficient. Respondents scored lowest in evaluation, which reflects their ability to critically assess texts. Recent literature by McKeown et al. (2020) highlights that evaluation skills are crucial for developing critical thinking. The authors suggest that integrating diverse texts and perspectives into instruction can enhance students' evaluative skills, indicating a potential area for growth in future instructional designs.

Lastly, Appreciation with a Mean Score of 2.10 is marked Not Proficient. The lowest score in appreciation signifies a struggle to engage with texts on a personal or aesthetic level. Research by Dewey (2021) argues that fostering a love for reading and appreciation for literature is vital for lifelong engagement with texts. Incorporating more engaging materials and discussions around the emotional and aesthetic aspects of reading could enhance appreciation skills.

These findings reveal that while respondents show moderate proficiency in literal comprehension and reorganization, they face challenges in inferential, evaluative, and appreciation skills. The literature underscores the importance of targeted instructional

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strategies to address these gaps. By leveraging scaffolding techniques, such as film viewing, educators can create a more dynamic learning environment that supports the development of these essential reading comprehension skills.

Posttest Scores of the respondents after using film as a scaffolding strategy

Table 2
Posttest scores of the respondents after using the film as a scaffolding strategy in reading comprehension

Measure	Very Proficient	Moderately Proficient	Less Proficient	Not Proficient	Total Mean (N)	Score	Verbal Interpretation	
	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)				(1)
Literal	10 (33%)	10 (33%)	8 (27%)	1(3%)	1 (3%)	30	3.90	Very Proficient
Reorganization	1 (3%)	14 (47%)	11 (37%)	3 (10%)	1 (3%)	30	3.37	Moderately proficient
Inferential	4 (13%)	11 (37%)	7 (23%)	6 (20%)	2 (7%)	30	3.30	Moderately proficient
Evaluation	1 (3%)	7 (23%)	8 (27%)	8 (27%)	6 (20%)	30	2.63	Less proficient
Appreciation	0 (0%)	4 (13%)	14 (47%)	8 (27%)	4 (13%)	30	2.60	Not proficient

Legend:
 VP-Very Proficient (5) ; P-Proficient (4) ; MP- Moderately Proficient (3) ; LP-Less Proficient (2) ; NP- Not Proficient (1)

Table 2 shows clear and concise overview of the respondents' performance in various aspects of reading comprehension after using film as a scaffolding strategy

A significant proportion of respondents scored "Very Proficient" with the Mean Score of 3.9 showing a strong proficiency in literal comprehension and indicating that there is effective understanding of the basic elements of the texts.

In terms of Reorganization, the mean score is 3.37 which is interpreted as Moderately Proficient. The moderate proficiency in reorganization suggests that while respondents can summarize and synthesize information, they may still struggle with more complex restructuring tasks.

Exploring further, Inferential comprehension has a Mean Score of 3.30 which is interpreted as Moderately Proficient. The score in inferential comprehension indicates that respondents are making reasonable inferences but still require improvement.

In terms of evaluation, the Mean Score is 2.63 which is interpreted as Less Proficient indicating a need for improvement in this area. The lower mean score in evaluation points to challenges in critically assessing texts. This highlights the need for additional scaffolding in evaluation strategies when using film.

However, Appreciation skills has a Mean Score of 2.6 which is interpreted as Less Proficient indicating significant room for growth. The results show that respondents have difficulty engaging with texts on an emotional and aesthetic level. This suggests that simply viewing films may not be sufficient to enhance literary appreciation without guided activities.

These findings revealed that using film as a scaffolding strategy can enhance specific aspects of reading comprehension, particularly literal and reorganization skills. However, significant gaps in evaluative and appreciation skills suggest that additional instructional strategies may be necessary.

Test of difference between pretest and Posttest

Table 3
Test of difference between pretest and posttest scores in using film viewing as a scaffolding strategy for improving reading comprehension

Reading Comprehension Skills	Pretest		Posttest		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
	M	SD	M	SD				
Literal	3.50	1.31	3.90	1.03	-2.262	29	0.031	Significant
Reorganization	3.17	0.83	3.37	0.85	-1.185	29	0.246	Not significant
Inferential	2.67	0.92	3.30	1.15	-2.726	29	0.011	Significant
Evaluation	2.47	1.04	2.63	1.16	-0.724	29	0.475	Not significant
Appreciation	2.07	0.87	2.60	0.89	-2.283	29	0.030	Significant

Legend: $p \geq .05 = NS$; $p < .05 = S$

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Table 3 shows the comparative Means of the pre-test and post-test on the use of film viewing as a scaffolding strategy for improving reading comprehension. It is shown that among the five reading skills, the highest skill influenced by film viewing scaffolding is the Literal skill, followed by the reorganization, inferential, evaluation and appreciation.

In terms of literal comprehension, the significant improvement in literal comprehension scores ($p = 0.031$) suggests that film viewing effectively enhances students' recall of factual information. This means that the idea that films can reinforce textual information and help students remember key details more effectively.

Moreover, inferential comprehension with inferential comprehension scores ($p = 0.011$) indicates that students improved their ability to make inferences from the material.

In addition, appreciation of text that shows significant improvement in appreciation scores ($p = 0.030$) suggests that film viewing positively influences students' engagement with literature. This supports the notion that diverse media can enrich students' interpretative skills and enjoyment of texts.

However, in terms of reorganization and evaluation comprehension, the table shows the lack of significant differences in reorganization ($p = 0.246$) and evaluation ($p = 0.475$) scores that indicate that film viewing may not effectively support these aspects of comprehension. This implies that explicit teaching methods are essential to develop these higher-order thinking skills effectively. These key findings indicate that film viewing can significantly enhance specific areas of reading comprehension, particularly literal, inferential, and appreciation skills. However, for skills like reorganization and evaluation, a more integrated instructional approach may be necessary.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study focused grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students who served as the respondents of the study. Based on the significant findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn. First, the pre-test scores indicate that respondents exhibited moderate proficiency in literal and reorganization and encountered significant challenges in inferential, evaluation and appreciation. Second, the post-test results with the use of scaffolding strategy positively impacted respondents' reading comprehension skills, particularly in literal and reorganization. Lastly, there is significant differences between pre-test and post-test scores in reorganization and evaluation comprehension skills, thus these variables are partially sustained.

Established from the summary of findings and conclusions previously discussed, several recommendations are hereby presented. Teachers should continue the use films as a scaffolding strategy to support literal, inferential and appreciation skills and further develop focused strategies to enhance those skills. Given that there was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores in reorganization and evaluation skills, allocate more class time to activities that enhance these skills. This could include group discussions or real-world scenarios that require students to reorganize and evaluate information. Additionally, students should improve reorganization and evaluation skills possibly through interactive discussion and analytical tasks to enhance comprehension. Lastly, future researchers may conduct parallel studies to a wider scale and across curriculum for more comprehensive findings.

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